

ASSESSING THE PERFORMANCE OF POLICE CIVIL SERVANTS (SATPOL PP) OFFICERS IN ENFORCEMENT OF PUBLIC ORDER: EMPIRICAL STUDY OF DISCIPLINE AND ETHICS

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Received: 05/03/2026 | Revised: 15/03/2026 | Accepted: 06/04/2026 | Published: 26/04/2026

Abstract

This study examines the performance of Satpol PP officers in enforcing public order, with a particular focus on work discipline and ethical behavior as fundamental aspects of public service accountability. Despite a clear legal mandate given to Satpol PP, challenges remain in ensuring that law enforcement practices are carried out in accordance with ethical standards and professional norms. This study aims to analyze how the legal framework and organizational factors influence the actual implementation of public order enforcement by Satpol PP officers. This study uses a normative-juridical approach combined with empirical qualitative methods. The normative analysis was conducted by examining laws and regulations, codes of ethics, and standard operating procedures that govern the authority and duties of Satpol PP. Empirical data were collected through in-depth interviews, field observations, and document analysis involving Satpol PP officers and relevant stakeholders at the local government level. The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify patterns and discrepancies between legal norms and field practices. The findings indicate that the gap between normative regulations and empirical implementation is influenced by factors such as leadership practices, organizational culture, legal understanding, and internal oversight mechanisms. These factors significantly influence the consistency of discipline and ethical behavior in enforcing public order. This study makes a practical contribution by offering recommendations for strengthening legal compliance, ethical governance, and performance evaluation mechanisms within the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP). Theoretically, this research enriches empirical legal studies by integrating normative analysis with field-based evidence in the context of public order enforcement.

Keywords: *Discipline, Ethics, Normative-Juridical, Batam, Public Enforcement, Satpol PP*

INTRODUCTION

Satpol PP is an apparatus formed in provinces and districts/cities to enforce regional regulations (Perda) and regional head regulations (Perkada), maintain public order, security and provide protection to the community (Britniantini & Ananta Prathama, 2023; Rahmadanita & Nurrahman, 2022). The legal basis for the formation of Satpol PP is regulated in Article 256 of Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, which is implemented through Government Regulation (PP) Number 16 of 2018 concerning Satpol PP (Fahmi et al., 2022; Januardi & Mayarni, 2025). Overall, the regulation stipulates that each regional government is required to establish a Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) through a Regional Regulation, which is directly responsible to the regional head through the regional secretary. In addition, Satpol PP is given non-judicial law enforcement authority, including disciplining and prosecuting citizens or legal entities who violate regional regulations or disturb public order, conducting investigations into alleged violations, and imposing administrative sanctions. In carrying out these duties, Satpol PP acts as a coordinator for regional Civil Servant Investigators (PPNS) and can coordinate with other law enforcement officers. The performance of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) in maintaining public order is crucial for the effectiveness of regional law enforcement and the quality of public services. Good performance is reflected in the Satpol PP's ability to enforce regulations consistently and fairly, ensuring that regional regulations do not become mere paper tigers (Simanjuntak & Pratama, 2025). On the other hand, suboptimal performance can lead to various problems, including ineffective regional regulations and violations of public order, illegal street vendors,

unlicensed buildings, violations of health protocols, and others (Butarbutar, 2019) . The Indonesian Ombudsman noted that public reports on the Satpol PP's performance often lead to problems such as disputes between residents triggered by slow action on violations (compliant residents feel disadvantaged if violators are not prosecuted) (Ombudsman RI 2021). Paradoxically, the Satpol PP in many regions is considered ineffective in carrying out its role. This situation prompts a critical evaluation of the factors influencing the Satpol PP's performance, particularly the discipline and ethics of its members. Civil servant discipline and ethics are two important pillars in ensuring that the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) exercises its authority professionally and trustworthy. As part of the State Civil Apparatus (ASN), Satpol PP is required to uphold the civil servant oath and adhere to the Civil Servant Discipline Regulations (Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 16 of 2023). Government Regulation No. 94 of 2021 defines discipline as the ability to comply with obligations and avoid prohibitions stipulated in laws and/or official regulations, which, if not complied with, will result in disciplinary action.

Civil servant discipline includes the obligation to arrive at work on time, carry out duties responsibly, provide the best possible service to the public, refrain from abuse of authority, and prohibit a series of behaviors that violate regulations or demean civil servants. Disciplinary violations can result in varying degrees of sanctions, ranging from warnings to dishonorable discharge, depending on the severity of the offense. In addition to discipline, the code of ethics serves as a moral guideline for Public Order Unit (Satpol PP) officers in their actions. Satpol PP are expected not only to obey the law but also to uphold ethical values, such as justice, honesty, empathy, and respect for human rights (Indonesian Cabinet Secretariat 2018). As stipulated in the latest regulation (Minister of Home Affairs Regulation No. 16 of 2023), it contains 17 moral obligations for each member including: believing in and being devoted to God Almighty; upholding Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution; Upholding the oath/promise of civil servants; complying with civil servant discipline; being polite and friendly to the community; upholding legal, religious, human rights, and social norms; maintaining image and honor; working honestly and professionally; avoiding reprehensible actions and not abusing authority or trading agency assets.

The purpose of this code of ethics is to uphold professionalism and a positive image. Thus, discipline and ethics are complementary: discipline ensures compliance with formal rules, while ethics ensures that rules are enforced morally and civilly. The reality on the ground demonstrates the gap between normative standards and empirical conditions. Several incidents have come to public attention, from violent or excessive actions during street vendor raids, which have been criticized as inhumane, to Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) officers being involved in extortion that has damaged the agency's image. However, there are also positive examples where Satpol PP has successfully carried out its duties firmly yet humanely, such as enforcing Covid-19 health protocols through persuasive outreach in Lampung, demonstrating the application of good ethics, resulting in greater public acceptance. These diverse conditions highlight the need for empirical studies to assess the extent to which discipline and ethics have been upheld in Satpol PP operations and how this impacts the performance of public order enforcement.

This study seeks to answer the following questions: What is the legal framework governing the discipline and ethics of Satpol PP members and the role of Satpol PP in enforcing public order; what are the empirical conditions of the implementation of discipline and code of ethics in Satpol PP in several regions, and their impact on the performance of regional regulation enforcement; what are the challenges faced by Satpol PP regarding the implementation of ethics and enforcement of disciplinary sanctions; how effective is internal and external supervision; and how does the public respond to the performance of Satpol PP. The urgency of this research is based on the position of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) as the vanguard of law enforcement and public order services. The research findings are expected to contribute to policy development to enhance the capacity of Satpol PP, implement more effective oversight and sanction mechanisms, and strengthen a work culture of integrity. Ultimately, improved Satpol PP performance will impact the enforcement of legal authority at the local level, create an orderly and conducive community environment, and increase public trust in local government.

METHOD

This study uses a normative-juridical approach combined with qualitative empirical research. The normative-juridical approach is used to analyze the legal framework governing the authority, duties, and responsibilities of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) in enforcing public order, including applicable laws and regulations, the officer's code of ethics, and standard operating procedures (SOPs). The normative analysis aims to understand the legal basis and ethical norms that should guide the implementation of Satpol PP officers' duties. A qualitative empirical approach was used to examine legal provisions and ethical norms as they are implemented in enforcing public order. Empirical data were collected through in-depth interviews, field observations, and documentation studies. Interviews were conducted with members of the Batam City Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) and other parties selected purposively

based on their involvement and experience in enforcing public order. Field observations were conducted to obtain a factual picture of officer behavior, work patterns, and interactions in carrying out their duties, while documentation studies were used to examine activities, internal documents, and institutional work guidelines. The data obtained were analyzed qualitatively using thematic analysis techniques, namely by identifying, grouping, and interpreting key themes related to discipline, officer ethics, and public order enforcement performance. The analysis was conducted by comparing empirical findings with applicable normative provisions to identify any correspondence or gaps between legal norms and field practices. To increase data validity, this study applied triangulation of sources and techniques, so that the results of the analysis are expected to provide a comprehensive and in-depth picture of the performance of Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) officers in the context of public order enforcement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of Discipline and the Satpol PP Code of Ethics

Based on the research results, the implementation of discipline and the Civil Service Police Unit (Satpol PP) code of ethics showed varying results across regions. In general, the level of discipline of Satpol PP officers is reflected in adherence to working hours, attendance at roll call and patrols, execution of duties in accordance with standard operating procedures (SOPs), and the absence of legal violations by personnel. Meanwhile, the implementation of the code of ethics is reflected in the behavior of Satpol PP in interacting with the public, compliance with procedures and orders from superiors, and the absence of moral deviations such as extortion or abuse of power.

The results show that the level of compliance with formal discipline within the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is relatively high due to the existence of a binding personnel oversight mechanism. In many areas, Satpol PP has implemented electronic attendance and daily performance monitoring. Disciplinary sanctions will be imposed in accordance with Government Regulation Number 94 of 2021, which is easily enforced in the event of serious violations. For example, in Penajam Paser Utara Regency, East Kalimantan, the local Civil Service Office revealed that in the past two years, four Satpol PP civil servants have received severe disciplinary sanctions in the form of dismissal for serious disciplinary violations. Similarly, the Jakarta Satpol PP supervisory board has taken several firm actions against Satpol PP officers found to have violated the law, and all have been prosecuted and sanctioned to maintain the integrity of the corps.

From the investigation of the Indonesian Ombudsman's report and media coverage, several ethical issues in law enforcement have emerged: a repressive approach lacking empathy: Several Satpol PP law enforcement operations have been highlighted by the media for being deemed lacking in humanitarian principles, such as dismantling street vendor stalls or evict residential areas without adequate dialogue, confiscating small merchandise that is a source of livelihood, or using a harsh communication style. According to the Ombudsman, enforcement of regional regulations by Satpol PP is still considered "rough" and lacking a persuasive approach (Ombudsman RI 2021). In fact, the value of social justice requires law enforcers to consider the proportion and conditions of violators; this was expressed by Abidin & Turmudi (2023) regarding street vendor regulations in city X resulting in clashes because street vendors felt treated unfairly; this reflects the dilemma between demands for regulation and social justice raised by Saputra.

Furthermore, there are administrative errors and negligence when Satpol PP personnel fail to act when they should. The Ombudsman has recorded public reports of Satpol PP being negligent or slow in responding to violations of local regulations, resulting in conflict between. For example, a neighbor builds a building that violates regulations and one party reports it, but Satpol PP fails to act and causes a dispute (Gea et al., 2026). This negligence is not a matter of violence, but rather an ethical aspect of responsibility and accountability; according to the Indonesian Ombudsman (2017), this action is a form of administrative error (failure to provide services as they should); and shows that Satpol PP ethics also include performance ethics to work quickly, responsively and not allow violations to occur, because allowing violations to occur can be considered a disregard for justice for law-abiding citizens.

Implementation of duties that does not comply with SOPs further reveals that in several areas, the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) does not have or does not follow standard SOPs, resulting in "disorderly" actions in the field and varying standards. For example, law enforcement procedures that should be carried out through procedures (written warnings, coordination with relevant agencies) are sometimes ignored, or documentation of law enforcement actions is incomplete. This is problematic because it relates to legal certainty and accountability. Integrity and abuse of authority: There have been cases of Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) officers engaging in extortion, illegally protecting nightclubs, or exploiting the public for personal gain. Such cases sometimes arise during arrests by law enforcement officers. While relatively rare, they damage the overall reputation of Satpol PP. Internally, when officers

are caught, they are usually immediately dishonorably discharged for serious violations of discipline and ethics, such as honesty and abuse of authority. Some local governments are responsive to integrity issues: for example, the Jakarta Satpol PP has collaborated with the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) to educate its officers on anti-corruption. Despite the above challenges, best practices in enforcing discipline and ethics were also identified. For example, in research by Purnomo et al. (2021), the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) successfully implemented ethical service during law enforcement operations. Officers were polite yet firm, prioritizing education. Consequently, the public was more receptive to enforcement of health regulations because they felt they were being treated with respect. The involvement of female Satpol PP officers in operations (to reprimand female violators) also fostered a more humane approach.

Furthermore, the Yogyakarta Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is known for its humane approach to controlling street vendors, employing dialogue and relocation before taking action. They implement tiered early warnings for violators, in accordance with clear standard operating procedures (SOPs). This aligns with the code of ethics regarding polite behavior and avoiding actions that harm the public before persuasion efforts are complete. In some areas, adherence to time discipline and hierarchy within the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is considered quite good. Morning and afternoon attendance is routinely recorded, and patrol activities are reported daily. Members absent without a valid reason are immediately reprimanded. For example, the Sleman Regency Satpol PP reported a personnel attendance rate approaching 100% after implementing a strict reward and punishment system for absenteeism. Rewards are given in the form of incentives for diligent and successful teams, and penalties are given in the form of administrative sanctions for indiscipline. This demonstrates that internal discipline management can effectively improve performance.

The performance of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) in enforcing regional regulations and public order, as a result of the implementation of discipline and ethics, still requires improvement in various regions. According to (Gea et al., 2026), the role of Satpol PP is considered inactive and ineffective, because many regional regulations cannot be enforced, this is caused by limited personnel and budget, the quality of human resources, support from regional heads and challenges in coordination with other agencies. This performance weakness also stems from discipline and ethics factors: organizational discipline and bureaucratic ethics that make personnel mentality reluctant to patrol due to limited resources or feeling their duties are not appreciated, resulting in low motivation. Low budget support for Satpol PP causes some officers to be reluctant, some even involved in extortion or inappropriate behavior, due to low salaries and welfare. This is a serious problem because it concerns ethics and integrity for inadequate welfare can erode integrity if not balanced with supervision and personal commitment.

On the other hand, if discipline can be enforced, the performance of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) will improve significantly. In other words, the most urgent internal solution to improve performance is to ensure that every member of the Satpol PP is disciplined. Discipline creates order and productivity, which in turn helps the Satpol PP achieve its law enforcement targets better. This is evident in public order raids, where personnel are fully present and ready on time, they can reach more locations than those who are frequently late or understaffed due to absenteeism. Another finding related to the composition of the Satpol PP's human resources is also worth highlighting: ideally, all Satpol PP members should be civil servants in accordance with Law 23/2014, but in reality, many regions still rely on non-ASN personnel for operations. In a case study in Jatinegara District, East Jakarta, it was noted that the Satpol PP structure at the sub-district level consisted of approximately 90 personnel, consisting of civil servants, non-permanent employees (PTT), and individual service providers (PJLP). The significant involvement of non-civil servants (PTT/PJLP) requires different management, particularly in terms of shorter discipline and competency and lower welfare than civil servants, so their motivation and understanding of ethics may not be as strong as civil servants. This can impact the quality of the team's overall performance if not addressed through comprehensive training and strict supervision.

Ethical Challenges, Sanction Implementation and Oversight

Based on the above findings, challenges can be identified related to the ethics and enforcement of disciplinary sanctions in the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP), as well as aspects of oversight and community response: ethical dilemmas in law enforcement are often faced when enforcing regulations that affect the lives of ordinary people. Enforcing public order regulations, prohibiting street vendors or prohibiting illegal building construction without alternative solutions are often criticized as inconsistent with a sense of social justice. The principle of legality versus humanity becomes a tug-of-war. From a regulatory perspective, the Satpol PP is obliged to enforce regulations to ensure law and order in the city (Kurniawan Saputra et al., 2018; Saputra et al., 2023).

However, from a public ethics perspective, Satpol PP officers are required to understand social situations. Street vendors operate out of economic necessity, and squatters may lack access to adequate housing. Saputra et al. (2023) emphasize the need to internalize just and civilized humanitarian values and social justice into Satpol PP standard operating procedures (SOPs) to ensure more legitimate and sustainable enforcement of regional regulations. The challenge is that Satpol PP officers must balance two things: enforcing regulations firmly but in a humane manner. In practice, not all personnel are trained for this. Article 21 of PP 16/2018 outlines Satpol PP's obligation to uphold human rights and act without discrimination. However, technical training is often prioritized over skills training. Basic training on human rights, persuasive communication, and social engineering is needed for Satpol PP officers; without this understanding, ethical challenges will continue to arise and risk creating conflict with the community. Normatively, the rules for sanctions are clear. The challenge lies in consistently enforcing them within the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP). There are concerns that personal ties or political interference could lead to inappropriate sanctions being imposed. Therefore, the establishment of the Code of Ethics Council (MKE) and Internal Action Officer (PTI) in Minister of Home Affairs Regulation 16/2023 is expected to reduce subjectivity.

Another challenge is how to enforce sanctions against contract workers, which are not formally regulated in disciplinary regulations. In practice, the head of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) has the authority to terminate or not renew the contracts of problematic contract workers. However, transparency is needed to avoid arbitrary accusations. Fostering discipline among contract workers requires specific regional policies, such as gubernatorial or regental regulations on codes of ethics for non-civil servant employees. Without clear regulations, volunteer workers may feel treated differently or less fairly than civil servants. This can affect their morale. Public scrutiny also occurs spontaneously through social media. Public order officers' actions in the field are easily recorded and shared. This is a double-edged sword: on the one hand, it encourages greater vigilance, but on the other, even minor incidents can go viral and create negative perceptions. Many Public Order Officers (Satpol PP) admit to reminding their officers to always behave politely because of the ubiquity of cameras. This is actually an effective form of social control, encouraging officers to uphold public ethics. The performance of Public Order Officers (Satpol PP) is often under public scrutiny. Public responses to Public Order Officers (Satpol PP) tend to vary depending on their experiences. For those who benefit from order, Public Order Officers (Satpol PP) are viewed positively as guardians of order. Conversely, for those affected by such control, Public Order Officers (Satpol PP) can be viewed negatively and even as tools of government repression.

Some regions have involved the community in Satpol PP activities: for example, the establishment of community protection units to assist Satpol PP at the sub-district level as the eyes and ears of the community. This also includes establishing communication forums with street vendors or local community leaders before major operations. This can increase public understanding that law enforcement is for the common good, not simply a matter of rigid enforcement. When the community feels involved or informed beforehand, their response tends to be more cooperative. To achieve this ideal model, recommendations have emerged from various parties, for example: the need to improve the overall human capacity of Satpol PP personnel. This includes not only physical skills but also education in law, human rights, sociology, and public ethics in the Satpol PP training curriculum. The Ministry of Home Affairs, through the Regional Government Training Center (Pusdiklat Pemda), can design a curriculum that incorporates these modules. Regional budgets need to be allocated adequately for Satpol PP operations, as these factors affect morale and corps pride.

Furthermore, the seriousness of regional heads in utilizing the Satpol PP (Public Order Agency) is also crucial. Some regional heads underutilize the Satpol PP, even assigning them to trivial tasks such as parking attendants or office security. As a result, the Satpol PP's primary role is distorted and its image is tarnished. Ideally, regional heads would provide full support and position the Satpol PP in accordance with its core duties: enforcing regional regulations and public order. When top leaders are committed, the Satpol PP typically has greater confidence in their actions on the ground, under political auspices. Based on the results presented, several key points can be discussed regarding the discipline and ethics of Satpol PP, the challenges in implementing sanctions, the effectiveness of supervision, community response, and the ideal model of Satpol PP in the future. The significance of discipline and ethics to performance emphasizes that discipline and ethics are not peripheral aspects, but rather the core of Satpol PP performance. Discipline is a prerequisite for creating consistent action; without discipline, Satpol PP cannot consistently enforce the rules. Furthermore, it is a prerequisite for Satpol PP actions to be accepted as legitimate by the community. Optimal performance is achieved when rules are enforced and the community supports them. Challenges in Implementing Disciplinary Sanctions: Although a legal framework for disciplinary sanctions exists, their implementation in regional bureaucracies consistently faces cultural challenges. Violations are sometimes allowed to go unpunished under the guise of family development. In the long run, this is counterproductive because

it creates morale risks. For the semi-military Satpol PP (Public Order Agency), the culture of hierarchy and discipline tends to be stronger than for other regional government institutions. However, the challenge primarily arises at the leadership level: do they have the courage to take action against members who violate, especially if there are multiple violations, as this also reflects a failure of leadership to provide guidance. Therefore, a Code of Ethics Council mechanism can help shift the burden of sanction decisions from individual superiors to a collective forum, resulting in more objective decisions.

Another challenge is transparency. The public is often unaware that the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) has punished internal individuals, leading to the perception that they are above the law. Discussion suggestion: Satpol PP could adopt the National Police's transparency approach in handling internal violations. This would have a deterrent effect internally and restore trust externally. Of course, this aspect needs to be regulated so as not to violate privacy but sufficiently convey the message that the organization will not tolerate violations. Ethical Challenges: Humanist vs. Firm – Discussions about the ethics of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) always boil down to one key word: "humanist." Post-reformasi, demands for a humanist approach to Satpol PP have increased, particularly due to public memories of the militaristic law enforcement style of the previous era. Being humane yet firm is a difficult but achievable goal. These efforts include: recruiting Satpol PP members with an eye for demeanor, not just physical attributes; training in effective communication; formulating standard operating procedures (SOPs) that include persuasive steps before using violence; and introducing a restorative justice approach on a micro-scale.

From an integrity perspective, the ideal model for a Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is one with a strong anti-corruption culture. Ideally, Satpol PP members have a code of honor and uphold it. There is zero tolerance for extortion or bribery. Externally, Satpol PP earns public trust, so that when warnings or operations are issued, citizens tend to comply, not simply out of fear, but because they believe that Satpol PP's actions are in the public interest. Of course, the ideal model above is a long-term goal. The reality is that achieving it requires diverse improvements: regulations are well-directed, but consistent implementation, support from regional leaders, improved human resource quality, and a more holistic work culture are needed. In other words, the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) must transform from the stigma of "evictors" to a more holistic "police maintenance."

Policy Implications: This discussion contains several important policy implications. First, the need for Satpol PP recruitment in accordance with legal mandates: the large number of honorary staff in Satpol PP must be addressed, either through gradual appointments according to formation or restructuring. Second, the importance of budget and facilities: without tools and support, self-discipline alone is insufficient, as it will lead to frustration with the situation. Third, encourage the establishment of internal regulations/Perkada: some regions may need to establish a Regional Head Regulation on the Satpol PP code of ethics and detailed SOPs, adapting Permendagri 16/2023 to the local context. Fourth, strengthen the Satpol PP institution: for example, the status of the Satpol PP head should be equal to that of other important institutions.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that the performance of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) in enforcing public order is largely determined by the level of discipline and ethical practices of its members. Normatively, the legal framework provides a strong foundation: Law 23/2014 affirms the mandate of the Satpol PP, Government Regulation 16/2018 regulates its authority and requires Satpol PP to work in accordance with SOPs and a code of ethics, Government Regulation 94/202 binds Satpol PP members to comply with discipline, and Minister of Home Affairs Regulation 16/2023 clarifies the operational standards and professional code of ethics of the Satpol PP along with its oversight mechanisms. Normatively, the ideal model of the Satpol PP is a professional law enforcer with integrity, upholding human rights, discipline, and humanity in carrying out its duties. Empirically, this situation demonstrates a gap between ideals and the reality of implementation. On the one hand, there are Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) units with good discipline and a strong work ethic that effectively enforce local regulations with relatively few complaints. Studies and cases in some units show that when discipline is maintained and ethics are upheld, performance outcomes are very positive: public compliance increases and operational targets are achieved. On the other hand, common obstacles remain, such as internal disciplinary violations, both by individuals and institutions. Ethical violations occur in the form of less than humane law enforcement approaches or maladministration, leading to public criticism and a decline in public trust. Contributing factors include limited human resources, a high proportion of honorary members with different disciplinary rules, a lack of specific training on ethics/human rights, a less professional organizational culture, and suboptimal infrastructure and budget support. The biggest ethical challenge for the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is balancing firm law enforcement with justice and humanity. Implementation often faces a social dilemma. Without strong ethical guidelines, the Satpol PP risks being perceived as overly repressive by the

public. Implementing internal disciplinary sanctions, despite strict regulations, requires consistency and commitment from leaders; if implemented firmly and fairly, it will strengthen a culture of discipline among all members. Internal oversight has been strengthened, but its effectiveness requires time and serious implementation. External oversight and public participation are important counterweights to the accountability of the Satpol PP. Overall, the performance of the Public Order Agency (Satpol PP) is undergoing a transformation toward more professional standards and integrity. While the legal framework and improvement efforts are in place, ultimate success depends on implementation at the regional level. The ideal Satpol PP is an institution that demonstrates firm discipline yet possesses a guardian spirit, carrying out its duties to enforce regional regulations not only by enforcing the law but also by fostering public legal awareness. To achieve this, improvements must encompass aspects of the Satpol PP's human resources, organization, budget, and work culture.

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